

Usability of Robot Avatars: a case study.

G. Zambella¹, G. Grioli^{1,2}, A. Cavaliere², G. Rosato², C. Petrocelli², M. Poggiani², M. Barbarossa², G. Lentini², E. Sessa², V. Tincani², A. Bicchi^{1,2}, M. G. Catalano²

Abstract—The interest in avatars designed for real-world applications has grown significantly in recent years. Increasing the adoption of these platforms inevitably requires putting users at the core of their development process.

With this objective in mind, we conducted a usability study of the avatar robot Alter-Ego X, a soft, two-wheeled, semi-anthropomorphic robot. This study involves various subjects with diverse technological and educational backgrounds. After a brief training phase, each subject performed tasks extracted by the Ana Avatar XPRIZE and, based on this experience, evaluated the system in terms of general usability and task-specific workload. Results show that using Alter-Ego X as an avatar is relatively easy even for non-experts. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this work represents one of the first studies evaluating the use of an avatar in terms of usability, intuitiveness, and ease of use.

I. INTRODUCTION

The concomitance of technological developments ranging from collaborative robotics [1], [2], [3] to consumer VR technologies [4], has accelerated the design and development of avatars, i.e. platforms remotely controlled by human users, to explore the robot's surroundings and engage in remote physical interactions.

The clearest evidence of this claim is probably the interest shown by major companies and funding agencies in promoting competitions and prizes for the first ones capable of transporting human presence and skill to distant locations in real time. Notable examples are the 2015 DARPA Robotics Challenge [5] and the recent Avatar Xprize by All Nippon Airways (ANA), which put up \$10 million as a prize ¹.

The real goal is shifting from the development of basic technologies to the integration of the latter that can push the diffusion of robot avatars in the world to the level of smartphones and laptops. Indeed, even the ANA Avatar Xprize specifically focused on developing *user-friendly* avatars that should enable individuals to navigate and manipulate the physical world remotely, providing a previously unattainable sense of embodiment and immersion.

However, the widespread adoption of avatar technologies cannot avoid to put users at the center of the technological design process. In this, engineers should consider both from the perspective of pilots operating the avatar and that of other bystanders that could be interacting with the robot in different ways. One of the fundamental steps of this process is the identification of suitable metrics to measure the usability of the robot avatar systems and its their impact on the users' mental and physical fatigue.

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²Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, via Morego, 30, 16163 Genova, Italia

¹<https://avatar.xprize.org/prizes/avatar>

Fig. 1: In this figure, the ANA Avatar Xprize snapshots of the tasks we chose for the usability study.

In this work, we present a study of the usability of a robot avatar and the evaluation of its workload. Specifically, we assess the usability of Alter-Ego X [6] ², a soft, modular, lightweight, two-wheeled semi-anthropomorphic robot that we have developed for the ANA Avatar Xprize. Additionally, a simple, lightweight pilot station, which can be easily worn, enables users to immerse themselves in Alter-Ego and control it remotely. To enhance the immersion experience, haptic and visual feedback interfaces are integrated in a modular way. To evaluate its usability and the task-oriented workload requirement of the Alter-Ego X teleoperation experience, we exploit the System Usability Scale (SUS) test [7] and the NASA Raw Task Load Index (NASA-RTLX) [8].

II. USABILITY STUDY

To evaluate the usability of robot avatar, we conducted experiments with non-experts. These experiments were inspired by the ANA Avatar Xprize and consisted of two main phases: the training and the run test.

The training phase requires the teleoperator and the robot avatar are in the same room and it is divided into two parts: i) the teleoperation without the headset, and ii) the teleoperation with the headset. The first part allows the participants to familiarize with the joystick controls and to show them how their arm movements are mapped on the robot arms. In the second part (i.e., the teleoperation with the headset), instead, participants try to perform the tasks that would be evaluated during the run test. The maximum duration for the training phase is set to 25 minutes.

During the run test phase, as in the ANA Avatar Xprize, the teleoperator and the robot avatar are placed in different rooms. For this phase, 6 tasks out of the 10 tasks specified in the ANA Avatar Xprize are selected:

- 1) *Interaction*: the Avatar reports to the Mission Commander and introduces themselves (Fig. 1a);
- 2) *Grasping*: the Avatar activates a switch (Fig. 1b);
- 3) *Navigation*: the Avatar navigates along the room avoiding obstacles (Fig. 1c);

²Alter-Ego X is an open-source project available online at <https://www.naturalmachinemotioninitiative.com/ego>.

Fig. 2: In this figure, we reports the SUS score of each participant and the final one.

Fig. 3: This figure shows the NASA-RTLX indices for each task. We also report the max and min values obtained for each index.

- 4) *Weight Estimation*: the Avatar must identify the full battery canisters that are among empty canister (Fig. 1d);
- 5) *Manipulation*: the Avatar places the correct canister into the designated slot (Fig. 1e);
- 6) *Haptics*: the Avatar must reach through the barrier to identify the rough textured rock (Fig. 1f).

The maximum duration of the run is 20 minutes and it concludes under four main circumstances: i) if the participant successfully completes all the tasks before reaching the maximum duration of the run; ii) if the maximum duration of the run is reached before the participant completes all the tasks; iii) if the participant decides not to continue with the run test, and iv) if the robot experiences a breakdown during the run test, rendering it impossible to continue. In case of an emergency, the expert present in the room with the robot has the authority to stop the task. In this situation, participants have the option to repeat the task once.

After the run test, the participants complete two questionnaires: i) the System Usability Scale (SUS) questionnaire [7], and ii) the NASA-RTLX one [9].

III. ALTER-EGO X USABILITY RESULTS

To conduct this study on usability, we used the Alter-Ego X platform we developed for the ANA Avatar Xprize, and we carried out experiments with 12 non-experts between the ages of 21 and 39, comprising 7 males and 5 females.

Fig 2 reports the SUS scores obtained for each participant (blue columns) and the final SUS value of the platform (green column). The latter is equal to 74.17, i.e., Alter-Ego X's usability level is considered acceptable ([10]). Additionally, according to [4], this value is close to the SUS score of VR products such as Oculus Rift DK2 (82.9) and Gear Vr (82.7).

To conclude, Fig 3 depicts the results obtained from the NASA-RTLX test. It is possible to notice that tasks like Interaction, Grasping, Navigation, and Full Alter-Ego Experience present a NASA-RTLX index ranging from 10 to 29, which corresponds to medium average workload requirements. On the other hand, tasks like Weight Estimation, Manipulation,

and Haptics exhibit a somewhat high level of workload requirement. Indeed, the NASA-RTLX indices relative to these tasks range from 30 to 49. Taking into account that there is no significant difference between NASA-RTLX and NASA-TLX indices [9], it is possible to compare the NASA-RTLX index of the full Alter-Ego X experience with the results presented in [11] for common tasks, such as daily tasks, driving cars, computer activities, and so on. The full Alter-Ego X experience requires a workload level higher than that of daily tasks, such as engaging in conversation, completing a telephone inquiry, and using a home medical device. However, it is lower than the workload level required for navigation tasks, tracking tasks, video game playing, and robot operations.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, we presented a study on the usability and workload of the use of robot avatars. To perform this investigation, we used Alter-Ego X, the two-wheeled semi-anthropomorphic robot that we developed for the ANA Avatar Xprize. Results obtained from the SUS test and the NASA-RTLX questionnaire show that using Alter-Ego X as an avatar is relatively easy even for non-experts and that, on average, it exhibits a medium workload requirement. Despite the encouraging results, the validation shows us further necessary improvements and the importance of such kinds of validations in the design and control process to speed up the diffusion of these technologies.

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REFERENCES

- [1] G. Lentini et al. Alter-ego: A mobile robot with a functionally anthropomorphic upper body designed for physical interaction. *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine*, 26(4):94–107, 2019.
- [2] N. Tsagarakis et al. The design of the lower body of the compliant humanoid robot “cub”. In *2011 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, pages 2035–2040. IEEE, 2011.
- [3] M. Grebenstein et al. The dlr hand arm system. In *2011 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, pages 3175–3182. IEEE, 2011.
- [4] R. Webster et al. System usability scale (sus): Oculus rift® dk2 and samsung gear vr®. In *2017 ASEE Annual Conference & Exposition*, 2017.
- [5] M. Spenko et al. *The DARPA robotics challenge finals: humanoid robots to the rescue*, volume 121. Springer, 2018.
- [6] G. Zambella et al. Usability of robot avatars designed for the real world: a case study. <https://www.dropbox.com/s/chic3duaafau8q6j/UsabilityAvatar.pdf?dl=0>. [Under Review].
- [7] J. Brooke. Sus-a quick and dirty usability scale. *Usability evaluation in industry*, 189(194):4–7, 1996.
- [8] M. Georgsson. Nasa rtlx as a novel assessment tool for determining cognitive load and user acceptance of expert and user-based usability evaluation methods. *European Journal of Biomedical Informatics*, 2020.
- [9] J. C. Byers et al. Traditional and raw task load index (tlx) correlations: Are paired comparisons necessary. *Advances in industrial ergonomics and safety*, 1:481–485, 1989.
- [10] A. Bangor et al. Determining what individual sus scores mean: Adding an adjective rating scale. *Journal of usability studies*, 4(3):114–123, 2009.
- [11] R. A. Grier. How high is high? a meta-analysis of nasa-tlx global workload scores. In *Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society Annual Meeting*, volume 59, pages 1727–1731. SAGE Publications Sage CA: Los Angeles, CA, 2015.